

OPPORTUNITY CLASS FOR THE NEWLY ARRIVED TIBETAN REFUGEE STUDENTS: STRUCTURE AND IMPLEMENTATION

Tenzin Dolma

Research Scholar

Department of Education (CASE)

Faculty of Education and Psychology

The Maharaia Savaiirao University of Baroda-390002 Vadodara

ABSTRACT

Integration of the newly arrived refugees into the mainstream education is one of the recurring challenges in refugee education. The present paper attempts to study the structure and implementation of the integration strategy that is adopted in the Tibetan refugee schools in India. For the newly arrived Tibetan refugee students in the Tibetan Children's Village Schools in India, a special class called "Opportunity Class" is provided. This paper examines the structure of this special class through the experience of the former Tibetan teachers who have taught in this school. The data for the present study were collected through semi-structured interviews. Thematic analysis is adopted for the data analysis. The data analysis generated five themes related to the structure and implementation: (1) Student Admission, (2) Teacher Recruitment, (3) Teaching -Learning Process, (4) Student Promotion, and (5) Facilities. Findings have implications for refugee integration around the world. Refugee integration strategies can be essential in addressing the challenges to facilitate a positive academic experience for newly arrived refugee students.

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Keywords: Refugee Integration, Tibetan refugee students, Opportunity Class, Structure and Implementation.

Introduction

Violence, persecution, and natural catastrophes have uprooted millions of people from their homes; hence, studying refugee education is crucial. Education empowers people to escape poverty and gain the resources necessary to engage in their communities (Shohel, 2020). According to Kakkar (2000), numerous academic studies have demonstrated the advantages of education in addressing the needs of refugees. However, despite being a fundamental human right, access to high-quality education remains a significant challenge for many refugees (Shohel, 2020). Only 61% of refugee children attend elementary school, compared to 91% of children worldwide. Challenges for refugee children grow as they become older. In secondary education, only 23% of refugee adolescents are enrolled compared to 84% worldwide (Cerna, 2019).

Globally, there were approximately 339,000 refugee births annually between 2018 and 2023. According to the United Nations Human Rights Convention (UNHCR, 2024), by the end of 2023, an

estimated 47 million (40%) of the 117.3 million persons forcefully relocated were children under the age of 18. As of April 2024, 7.2 million refugee children are missing out on education (Five Takeaways from UNHCR's 2024 Education Report, 2024). Refugee children's education is comparatively less studied than research on the education of immigrant children. For the successful integration of newly arrived refugee students, it is crucial to address the refugee students' diverse learning, emotional and social needs (Cerna, 2019).

Although there is currently no explicit law in India guaranteeing refugees the right to education, the country and other South Asian nations are parties to the 1967 protocol and the 1951 United Nations (UN) Convention related to the Status of Refugees. The Indian government provides protection and assistance to nearly 24,000 refugees and asylum seekers from different backgrounds (Bagade, 2015). India has granted asylum to nearby nations such as Bangladesh, Sri Lanka, Myanmar, Tibet, and Afghanistan (Mulchandani et al., 2019). Tibetans became refugees in India in 1950 when the People's Republic of China invaded Tibet. In March 1959, the Dalai Lama fled to India amid complex relations with the Chinese government and fearing for his safety, which led to a large-scale Tibetan exodus into India (Ahmad, 2012; Bisht, 2015; Gawas, 2023; Norbu, 2001; Samphel, 2009).

Tibetan refugees have been provided with separate schools by the Indian government to preserve their identity and cultural legacy without assimilating them (Palkyi, 2011).

There are 82 Tibetan schools in India, Bhutan, and Nepal. The four primary categories of Tibetan schools in India are those under the Central Tibetan Schools Administration, Tibetan Children's Village Schools, schools under the Central Tibetan Administration, and schools under the Tibetan Homes Foundation (Samphel, 2009). More than 24,000 Tibetan students are enrolled in these schools (Nair & Sharma, 2016). Due to necessity, Tibetan schools in exile have adopted English, Hindi, or Nepali as the medium of instruction and followed the curricula of their host nations (Ngodup, 1996). The Opportunity Class was introduced in the Tibetan Children's Village Schools in India to integrate the newly arrived Tibetan refugee students into regular school.

This paper aims to investigate how newly arrived Tibetan refugee students integrate into regular classes through the Opportunity Class in Tibetan Children's Village Schools in India and compare this process with global integration strategies.

Integration Strategies Around the World

The process by which refugee students are educated before being mainstreamed into regular classes varies from nation to nation. Newly arrived refugee children come from diverse backgrounds with different educational backgrounds. Thus, the actual pedagogical practices in those classes differ significantly from those in regular classes. The following outlines the educational frameworks and processes for newly arrived refugee children in the different nations.

1. Islamic Republic of Iran

The Islamic Republic of Iran has granted asylum to the largest number of refugees worldwide. As of 2024, there are approximately 3.8 million refugees (UNHCR, 2024). Afghan refugees are the largest refugee group in Iran. In the context of refugee education, the country has adopted 14 refugee educational policies developed by various executive entities between 1980 and 2020. Refugee students have the opportunity to attend Iranian public schools, and there are also self-governed Afghan schools for refugees from Afghanistan (Seddighi et al., 2022).

2. Germany

As of 2024, Germany has 2.7 million refugees (UNHCR, 2024). The newly arrived refugee students enrolled in preparatory or introductory classes for a period of two years. During that time, proficiency in the German language improves and bridges the gaps in education before transferring to regular classes. The specific school policy or the city determines the nature and the extent of the support after the transfer. Students with inadequate proficiency may receive additional support. Some of the Gymnasiums occasionally have preparation or introduction classes for refugee students. However, admission is often limited to students with proven academic levels or prior high school experience. Hauptschule or Realschule is where most of the refugee students in secondary education attend preparatory classes. These schools focus on lower and middle-level vocational education (Crul et al., 2019).

3. Turkey

With 3.1 million refugees in Turkey, the country is the second-largest refugee-hosting nation in the world (UNHCR, 2024). The Turkish Ministry of National Education (MoNE) established Temporary Education Centres (TECs) for newly arrived Syrian refugee students in Turkey. The TECs are private initiatives, and some of them are freely available with financial support from the Turkish Government, while others charge low fees. The TECs follow a curriculum identical to that of the Syrian schools (Seddighi et al., 2022). However, due to their placement in temporary institutions in Turkey, where the curriculum was in Arabic, the refugee children were unable to acquire Turkish, making it nearly impossible for them to transition to regular schools (Crul et al., 2019).

4. Sweden

In Sweden, the mapping of the newly arrived refugee students' prior academic experience, knowledge level, literacy skills, and mathematics skills begins within two months of their arrival. Based on this, the school determines the process for promoting students to the next grade and identifies any additional support that is needed. The early insertion of refugee students into regular education is the focus of the refugee integration model followed in Sweden (Koehler & Schneider, 2019).

5. Columbia

According to the UNHCR (2024), Colombia is one of the top refugee-hosting nations with approximately 2.8 million refugees. To support the education of newly arrived refugee students, the Ministry of National Education (MOE) and Migration Colombia have issued a series of national decrees and regulations (Coombes et al., 2024). The Camina Ren Secundaria, Juntos Aprendemos' education program allowed newly refugee students to bridge the academic gap and complete two grades in one year. The program also enhances the integration process by fostering the socio-emotional growth of refugee students (Payán-Luna, 2023).

Thus, in different nations, various integration strategies are employed to educate newly arrived refugee students before transitioning them into regular classes. The significant challenges observed among top refugee-hosting nations include inadequate facilities, a lack of qualified teachers, and financial constraints that hinder support for refugee education.

Newly Arrived Tibetan Refugee Students' Education in India

The Tibetan refugees are sent in groups of 30 to the Tibetan Refugee Reception Centre in Dharamsala, Himachal Pradesh, from the Tibetan Refugee Reception Centre in Kathmandu, Nepal. It was there that the children were kept apart from the adults by the reception authorities. After that, the concerned authorities distributed the children among several TCV schools according to their ages and the proximity of their relatives' houses or designated settlements (Gawas, 2023). Jetsun Pema, the sister of the Dalai Lama, formerly ran a network of schools for orphans and refugee children, known as the Tibetan Children's Village. Individuals who were too old to attend high school sometimes enrolled in South Indian Tibetan monastery colleges (Dorjee & Rigzin, 2024). Both Tibet-born and India-born students attend TCVs, but students attending other schools, such as CSTs or private schools, are often Tibetan students who were born in India and whose families can afford to pay for their education. Unaccompanied minors and children born in Tibet are housed and integrated into their new life at TCV schools since they are free of tuition and use a dormitory system for students (Gawas, 2023). The following are three central Tibetan Schools in India where newly arrived Tibetan refugee students are enrolled;

The Sherab Gatsel Lobling School

Tibetan Transit School (TTS), commonly known as Sherab Gatsel Lobling School in Himachal Pradesh, is a transit school for newly arrived Tibetan students aged 18 years and above. In this school, students acquire vocational skills and the Tibetan and English languages. For their overall development, the school provides a spiritual and cultural education in addition to instruction in the fundamentals of Tibetan and English. The Tibetan Reception Centre in Dharamsala officially launched it on April 1, 1993, with 103 young men and women. In 1998, the Department of Education of the Central Tibetan Administration (CTA) extended school terms from two to three

years. However, Students have been permitted to remain at the school for five years since 2000. In 2002, the Tibetan Reception Centre transferred the school to the Department of Education (DOE), under the CTA. On January 3, 2011, the DOE transferred the school administration to the Sambhota Tibetan Schools Society (STSS). This school offers correspondence courses from the College of Higher Tibetan Studies, as well as open schooling up to the +2 level, computer diploma courses, and food craft courses. The school has graduated 7502 young men and women to date (Sherab Gatsel Lobling School: Adult School for the Tibetan, n.d).

Tibetan Children's Village School

This school is one of the oldest educational institutions for Tibetan refugees in India, with its main branch located in Dharamsala, Himachal Pradesh. The school has educated more than half of the Tibetan population in exile. The school, located in Dharamsala, was initially established as a nursery centre. (Wangdu, 2019). There are branches of the Tibetan Children's Village (TCV) schools located in various places throughout India, including Selakui, Bylakuppe, Dharamshala, Gopalpur, Ladakh, and McLeod Ganj. The TCV school system provides free education to all Tibetan children and uses the hostel system to promote care for the underprivileged and orphaned (Gawas, 2023).

Tibetan Homes Foundation

Another school where newly arrived Tibetan refugee students are enrolled is the Tibetan Homes Foundation (THF). Rinchen Dolma Taring founded it in 1962, and the THF school's headquarters is located in Mussoorie. (Wangdu, 2019). THF runs four schools: two middle schools in Rishikesh (Gohri Mafi) and Dickyling, a senior secondary school in Mussoorie, and a secondary school in Rajpur. An Opportunity Class for newly arrived Tibetan refugees is available at Mussoorie's Tibetan Homes School (Tibetan Homes School, n.d.).

Research Methodology

This paper aims to study the integration process of newly arrived Tibetan refugee students through the Opportunity Class, drawing on the experiences of former teachers. This study is qualitative research. To better focus on this topic, the researcher has sought to answer the following two questions:

1. What is the structure and implementation of Opportunity Classes in Tibetan Children's Village Schools in India?
2. How do Tibetan refugees' integration strategies compare with those used in selected countries (e.g., Islamic Republic of Iran, Germany, Turkey, Sweden, Colombia)?

Data Collection

For the present study, the researcher employed purposive sampling to collect data from teachers who have taught English, Tibetan, and Mathematics in the Tibetan Children's Village

School. The researcher selected three participants (two male and one female teacher) who had taught between the 1990s and the 2000s for the study. All the participants were Tibetan-born individuals in India who held undergraduate degrees in their respective disciplines at the time of their recruitment as teachers at the Tibetan Children's Village School.

Data Analysis

The researcher employed thematic analysis for the data analysis in the present paper. The researcher recorded, coded, and categorised the data collected through semi-structured interviews with the teachers, then reorganised and grouped them according to themes and presented the findings.

Findings Of the Study

From the data analysis, the findings of the paper are;

From the data analysis, the researcher found that the structure and implementation of the Opportunity class for newly arrived Tibetan refugee students in the Tibetan schools in India are as follows: (1) Student Admission, (2) Teacher Recruitment, (3) Teaching -Learning Process, (4) Student Promotion, and (5) Facilities.

Student Admission

According to the teachers, all Tibetan refugee students under the age of 18 are eligible for enrolment in the Opportunity Class. The students enrolled in the opportunity class are under the age of 18. The division of students into different Tibetan Children's Village Schools depends on their age. Students below the age of 13 enrolled in the Tibetan Children's Village School Gopalpur, the Tibetan Children's Village School Pathlikuhl, the Tibetan Children's Village School Suja (Junior), and the Tibetan Children's Village School Upper Dharamsala. The students, aged 13 to 18, enrolled in the Tibetan Children's Village School Suja (Senior). The duration of the Opportunity Class is two years. If students enrolled at the end of the year, they must repeat the same class in the following year.

Teacher Recruitment

According to the teachers, there is no formal recruitment process in place for teachers in the Opportunity Class. The teachers assigned to teach the newly arrived Tibetan refugee students were trained teachers who were already working in the institute. All the teachers teaching in the Opportunity Class are of Tibetan origin. Teachers with qualified academic backgrounds are assigned to teach the Opportunity Class. The teachers either hold a B.Ed certificate or a Teacher Training Certificate (TTC). The Tibetan Children's Village Organisation previously offered the Teacher Training Certificate (TTC), and currently, Sarnath University also offers it. Due to the influx of refugee students into Tibetan schools during the 1990s and 2000s, a shortage of teachers arose at that time. As Teacher 1 stated;

“Sometimes there is an incidence where teachers with TGT (Trained Graduate Teacher) were assigned the role of Opportunity Class teacher.”

Teachers are neither trained nor provided with professional development programs to teach the newly arrived Tibetan refugee students, as there is a dearth of resources at that time.

Teaching-Learning Process

According to the teachers, the educational program for the Opportunity class was similar to that in grades V-X in terms of extracurricular activities. The newly arrived Tibetan refugee students in the Opportunity Class were assigned to different schoolhouses by the school and provided with music, art, and physical education classes. The English Language, Tibetan Language, and Basic Mathematics are the main subjects for students in the Opportunity Class, depending on their level of prior educational experiences. The school divides the students into different Opportunity Classes based on their prior school experiences and level of knowledge. As Teacher 1 stated;

“In our school, students are divided based on school experience and the medium of instruction in their previous school. Opportunity Class 1 has students without school experience, Opportunity Class 2 has students who have studied in schools with the Tibetan Language as a medium of instruction, and Opportunity Class 3 has students who have studied in schools with Chinese as the medium of instruction.”

There is no standard textbook for Opportunity class students. Teachers determine the learning materials and the methodology to use based on the different Opportunity Classes, taking into account their students' knowledge levels. The primary focus of the education in the Opportunity Class is language development.

Student Promotion

According to the teachers, the school determines the promotion of newly arrived Tibetan refugee students in the Opportunity Classes to regular classes based on their academic performance in the half-yearly and annual examinations at the end of the second year of the Opportunity Class. The teacher's recommendation and the students' ages also played a vital role in their promotion. As Teacher 2 stated;

The school generally promotes newly arrived Tibetan refugee students to grade IV in schools where students in the Opportunity Classes are below the age of 13. The schools promote students aged 13 to 18 in the Opportunity Class to grades IV through VI. For students between the ages of 13 and 18 who fail to pass the annual examination in the second year, the school sends them to a vocational school.

Facilities

According to the teachers, the facilities for students in the Opportunity Classes are the same as those for other students in the schools where newly arrived refugee students are enrolled. The

classroom of the opportunity class students is similar to that of the junior school classroom. The school provides students with three notebooks, one each for Mathematics, English, and Tibetan Language. Students are also provided with reading materials, as language development is a primary focus of education. However, the teacher indicated that there is no fixed classroom for the Opportunity class, as the number of students increases over time. As Teacher 3 stated;

“We do not have a fixed classroom for the Opportunity class. We take classes in whatever available space is inside the school campus.”

Discussion and Conclusion

The forced migration movement has peaked in recent years, creating severe challenges on a global scale. It has caused unprecedented humanitarian strife to both host nations and refugee communities (Altinkalp et al., 2019). Integration strategies adopted differ across nations; however, common implementation strategies include either direct enrolment in regular classes in mainstream schools or a preparatory class where language support is provided to newly arrived refugee students. In Iran, Afghan refugees either enrolled in Iranian public schools or studied in self-governed Afghan schools (Seddighi et al., 2022). Similarly, Temporary Education Centres (TEC) were established in Turkey for newly arrived refugee students (Crul et al., 2019). Columbia, on the other hand, has The Camina Ren Secundaria, Juntos Aprendemos' education program, which allows newly refugee students to bridge the academic gap and complete two grades in one year (Payán-Luna, 2023). However, Germany offers preparatory classes or introductory classes where newly arrived refugee students receive language support. Performance in these schools, as well as prior school experience, determines their promotion to higher classes (Crul et al., 2019; Jäger et al., 2021). In Sweden, the focus is on the immediate transition of refugee students into regular classes based on their prior knowledge level (Koehler & Schneider, 2019). Likewise, in India, Tibetan refugee students who are born in India are enrolled in Central School for Tibetans under Central Tibetan Administration run by Indian Government and those who are born in Tibet are enrolled in self-governed Tibetan schools in India with Tibetan Children's Village Schools in India being leading school for the newly arrived Tibetan refugee students below the age of 18 (Gawas, 2023). Those above the age of 18 enrolled in the Sherab Gatsel Lobling School (Sherab Gatsel Lobling School: Adult School for the Tibetan, n.d). Regarding the experience and challenges faced by the institution that has taught newly arrived refugee students, the findings revealed that (1) Teacher Workforce Shortages, (2) Diverse Student Proficiency Levels, (3) Language barriers, (4) Curriculum Relevance and Adaptation, and (5) Inadequate Resources.

A study of Ukrainian refugee students revealed that a lack of space and language barriers were the significant challenges to their integration into school education in host nations (Five Takeaways from UNHCR's 2024 Education Report, 2024). Similar findings were reported by

Antoniadou et al. (2023) in their study on the challenges faced by refugee students in Greece. Their study stated that Language problems, various mother languages and dialects, and the educational levels of the students are the biggest obstacles teachers encounter when educating refugee students. Thus, to have successful integration of the newly arrived refugee students, it is crucial to have schools with trained teachers and support staff that can help address the psychological and social needs of young children and adolescents recovering from the trauma of conflict. Thus, through training, preparing them for the refugee students in their classrooms, and providing resources to ease their problems, the policies should be adapted to maintain the motivation and efficacy of teachers' comprehension, even in different circumstances (EkiN & YetkiN, 2021).

The present paper highlights the structure and implementation of the “Opportunity Class”, a special class for the newly arrived Tibetan refugee students before they transferred to regular classes in the Tibetan Children’s Village school.

Based on the findings of the paper, the researcher recommended future research is recommended for a more comprehensive and detailed analysis study of the teaching strategies adopted by respective teachers, a comparative study between the Temporary Education Centre in Turkey and Tibetan Children’s Village Schools in India, different preparatory class in host nations particularly among the five countries hosting the most significant number of refugees: Turkey, Iran, Colombia, Germany and Uganda.

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